
Research Article

A new combination in *Pitcairnia* (Bromeliaceae)

Sanjeet Kumar^{1*} and Rajeev Kumar Singh²

¹Biodiversity and Conservation Laboratory, Ambika Prasad Research Foundation, Cuttack, Odisha, India

²Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

*E-mail: sanjeetaprf@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9538-397X>

Article Details: Received: 2025-12-16 | Accepted: 2026-02-06 | Available online: 2026-02-10

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Abstract: A new combination is proposed for *Pepinia werffii* H.Luther under the genus *Pitcairnia* L'Hér. as *P. werffii* (H.Luther) Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr.Singh.

Keywords: Endemic, Oxapampa, Pasco, *Pepinia werffii*, Peru

Introduction

Luther (2007) described *Pepinia werffii* based on specimens collected from Oxapampa, Pasco, Peru by H. van der Werff et al. in July 2003. Recently, Gouda (2025) transferred *P. werffii* H.Luther to the genus *Pitcairnia* L'Hér. as *P. werffii*, but for the basionym, he cited the pagination of the entire publication rather than the exact page. As a result, the combination is invalid under Article 41.5 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2025). Here, a new combination for *Pepinia werffii* H.Luther under *Pitcairnia* is proposed in accordance with Article 41.1 of the ICN (Turland et al. 2025).

New combination

Pitcairnia werffii (H.Luther) Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pepinia werffii* H.Luther, Selbyana 28(1): 5. 2007. *Pitcairnia werffii* (H.Luther) Gouda, Phytotaxa 722(1): 74. 2025, *nom. inval.*

Holotype: Peru, Pasco, Oxapampa, roadside Chatarra to Puerto Bermúdez, heavily logged forest, 700

m, 9 July 2003, *H. van der Werff, R. Vásquez, B. Grey, R. Ortíz & N. Davila 18187* (SEL).

Distribution: Endemic to Peru.

Acknowledgements

The second author is grateful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India (BSI), Kolkata and the Head of the Arid Zone Regional Centre, BSI, Jodhpur for providing facilities.

References

- Gouda, E.J. (2025). *Pitcairnia pseudoelliptica* (Bromeliaceae) a new species from Junin, Peru. *Phytotaxa* 722(1): 74–80. <https://doi.org/10.11646/phytotaxa.722.1.7>
- Luther, H.E. (2007). Miscellaneous new taxa of Bromeliaceae (XVIII). *Selbyana* 28(1): 5–12. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41760290>
- Turland, N.J., Wiersema, J.H., Barrie, F.R., Gandhi, K.N., Gravendyck, J., Greuter, W., Hawksworth, D.L., Herendeen, P.S., Klopffer, R.R., Knapp, S., Kusber, W.-H., Li, D.-Z., May, T.W., Monro, A.M., Prado, J., Price, M.J., Smith, G.F. and Zamora Señoret, J.C. (2025). International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Madrid Code). *Regnum Vegetabile* 162. University of Chicago Press, Chicago. <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226839479.001.0001>